

Corporate data warehouse development

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Abstract—*In order to share information distributed in a corporate unstructured informative system, it has been performed a market analysis and then started the design and the development of a data warehouse to retrieve, correlate, consolidate and then share data and information considered relevant to the Management Board. During the years, in fact, all the offices tried to manage their own processes by adopting systems deployed by each department other than the central IT, to work around the perceived or actual shortcomings of the central information systems This introduced security and compliance concerns and bad data, information and documents sharing behavior; other side effects are data redundancy, data inconsistency and data loss. This scenario forced the development of a structured data warehouse, a set of importing and data cleaning procedures and a web application for the data retrieval.*

Keywords—Database, Data Warehousing, OLAP, Information sharing, web development.

I. INTRODUCTION

In large public corporate environments, many times offices or single employees try to satisfy their own specific needs by adopting custom and non-structured solution, causing lack of data security and information sharing. Beside the relevant and critical security aspect, the problem due to the generation of information island, also called *silos*, is one of the main problems in such enterprises. This occurs also when there is an enterprise information management system, because in many cases initial requirements change during company's life, new projects force to record and manage new data unplanned in the original system, or simply because people try to simplify their daily work by looking for simply solution to complex problem, ignoring the general context.

Obviously there are hundreds of variables to consider before selecting the right solution to the problem; sometimes, when it is not possible starting from scratch, it could safer to adopt an integration solution that collects data from multiple sources and data providers, consolidate and correlate them and finally publish them in order to fill the gap between the original knowledge silos. This can overtake the complexity of rebuilding a complex environment, maximizing productivity and efficiency and minimizing the total cost ownership (TCO) satisfying under any circumstances to please the management.

II. RELATED WORK

All began with the initial general assessment to get as much information as possible regarding all the systems used by each office and user; these steps involved software and databases analysis, in depth process study and many interviews with people working on their daily tasks. The final report founded the basis on which build the overall needs, functionality specifications and constraints. Before starting to design the infrastructure and beginning coding, we performed a market analysis to find out a candidate solution that could give us the minimum time to market adoption of the software, but we were afraid by the supplier or the technology lock-in, so we decided to develop it in-house.

Here there are the main aspects to take care about:

- analyze and focus on the criteria with which to share data and information's;
- identify the figures who within the offices need to use those information's;
- develop organizational and management methods to make the information easier available to the figures indicated above;
- create an authorization criterion consistent with the general system;
- eventually modify existing technological tools;
- set up a system that foresees possible future integrations of databases with respect to those considered during the initial phase of project analysis, deriving for example from future needs;
- think about a solution that absolutely does not require consultancy or external supplies.

And these are the main functionality to focus on:

- web-based solution to allow easy use from all workstations but also from smart-devices such as smartphones or tablets;
- creation of a search engine that processes user requests and can satisfy them by analyzing a variety of attributes that vary over time;
- definition and management of different levels of authorization to the information's based on the current user;
- ease of use and immediacy in understanding the tool;
- recovery and correlation of information on companies and individuals distributed over many information systems;
- integration, over time, of information and data not currently available without the need for external consultancy;
- possibility of acquiring data from wide and heterogeneous systems such as databases of different technologies, structured files, personal productivity tools;

- guarantee that in no way processing or activity on the developing system can alter the original data;
- development of a solution capable of interfacing with existing technologies to exploit the infrastructure present in the company;
- modification, where necessary, of existing applications to ensure correct integration of information;
- ability to intercept any errors on the synchronization of the recovered data;
- reduced work overhead necessary for the correct functioning and maintenance of the application.

The initial data sources were 9 databases involving different technologies like Oracle 9, Sql Server 20xx, Excel and Access files stored in a NAS.

It is useful to take a refresh over the OLAP paradigm here, to clarify which approach has been applied for the development of the project. Typically an OLAP architecture provides that the data stored in a set of peripheral databases, through specific ETL policies (Extract, Transform, Load, i.e. extraction from the original data sources, processing and aggregation of those data and loading into a new database) are then saved in a target database, suitably sized and finally one or more services that access to the data (service in the wide sense of the term, a client-server software, a dedicated web application, a web service, an OLEDB driver,...).

Typically, the next step is the consolidation and correlation phase of the data that begins with de-normalization and analyzing the information using sophisticated tools by the technical staff and after that data are made available to the company management using a simplified user interface but which allows with less technical skills and above all with greater intuitiveness of querying data analysis.

Fig. 1: A typical butterfly OLAP architecture

By analyzing all the constraints found out during the definition of the specifications, those that most drove the design of the platform were the need to guarantee maximum flexibility over time, in the sense of being able to further integrate new data sources, that of the visibility of the individual attributes in relation to the current user and that of the reduced work overhead necessary for the correct operation and maintenance of the application.

The idea that therefore guided the design of the application was to consolidate all the information of the companies in a single matrix to then define in a new dedicated data architecture how this information could be organised, queried, filtered and displayed, by delegating to the application only the rendering on the screen of the retrieved information; on the other hand, as regards the consolidation of data from remote

sources, it was deemed effective and efficient enough to define a set of periodically scheduled migration procedures that would consolidate all the attributes of interest in the general matrix.

The design of the interface, on the other hand, required a specific approach because the constraint of not having to modify the source code over time in order to add further data sources and attributes did not make it possible to adopt the usual ASP.NET webforms. The number of pages, the arrangement of the controls available in them and their graphic layout and the other layout definitions are predetermined in the development phase; it was necessary to approach it in a completely different way, giving up the static nature of the objects but defining an operating logic that could dynamically instantiate them at runtime. This was made possible by delegating to a part of the database the task of containing the definition of the behavior of the pages and of the content and by designing an application which, by appropriately querying the database, was able to retrieve the information for the correct rendering of the pages, regardless of the subsequent integrations and capable of dynamically adapting to the new configuration. The behavior of the application, therefore, is entirely driven by the database and therefore it will not be necessary to modify the source code of the application to meet future needs.

The conceptual schema of the database can be split into two parts, one relating to the analyzed entities, the companies, and the other relating to the operations of the system. Both schemes have a linear structure, inheriting by the fact that you work substantially on the attributes of a company and on how they are represented in the application pages. For the first case, the conceptual scheme shows that there is a single entity, extended in terms of attributes, which is not related to other entities; this is essentially since the database consolidates a multiplicity of data coming from remote sources but that no facts or dimensions, typical of a data warehousing structure, are to be highlighted. Furthermore, it appears clear that the only two mandatory attributes in each tuple are the tax code used for the correlation of the data and the company name which constitutes, for the user, the only element of reference among the others; all other data may also not be present or valued. The available data will then be related to each other using the "Tax Code" attribute which uniquely identifies a company. The physical schema consists of the tables in the database which instantiate the identified entities in the logical-conceptual schema; further it has to be added the tables for the functioning of the application and for monitoring the data update.

Fig. 2: The physical database schema

As regard the Codd normal forms, all three are respected in the configuration tables while, also due to the very nature and intended use of the aggregate data matrix, the 2NF and 3NF have not been respected; in fact, there are fields containing non-atomic data and not all attributes are revealed directly to each tuple primary key.

The way to fill TuttoDB's database was conditioned by the nature of the project (independence from suppliers, tool maintainability over time, know-how of internal staff). Furthermore, the variety of platforms involved didn't allow for a single DLT tool in the consolidation database. Because of this, in the case of interfacing with Oracle databases, agents running on these servers are written which will carry out the CRUD operations, while in other cases, databases based on Microsoft technology or flat files residing in some point of the company, stored-procedures are written that are invoked by specific Maintenance plans on the database engine for data import. In both cases, a scheduled plan is running which every night provides for the alignment of the data. The following diagram schematically represents the data sources and the way in which the consolidation database is to be fed: on the one hand, for databases residing on RDBMS SQL Server, this will be done using stored procedures, on the other, for Oracle databases, thanks to agents residing on the relative servers.

Fig.3: ETL defined to import data

The structure of each stored procedure (but the same logic also applies to the agents in the Oracle servers) must provide for the insertion of new personal data when not detected in the target database (by verifying the existence of the CodiceFiscale – CF field), the updating of all the fields of interest (always by matching the CF and with the overwriting of all the other fields, the maintenance of the history is not required) and the removal of the data if the company no longer exists in the starting database; in this case the system does not a real record deletion but only an update to NULL for the pertinent fields in order not to eliminate information relating to companies that could still exist in another data source. For the execution of all the CRUD operations has been developed a single Stored-procedure which, through the use of a specific parameter, can complete all tasks in succession. The decision not to write dedicated stored-procedures for the three distinct phases originates from the idea of having fewer objects to manage (hence ease of management), all the code residing in a single script (reduced risk of forgetting parts of code to update) and less dependency between objects (each stored-procedure is atomic, it doesn't depend on or invoke any other). Each stored-procedure, beside migrating the data of interest, also appends

in the log table (TB_DWH_Log) the rows necessary to understand the outcome of the operation and detect any anomalies. The following diagram illustrates the structure of each stored procedure highlighting its main activities.

Fig. 4: Stored procedure structure

The highest level of the n-tier application is given by the presentation one which will be, in this case, a web-based user interface. It has been decided to pass parameters between one page and another through querystring to allow users share a link with other and give access to the exact views of the data; Since this is an intranet application not published directly to Internet except via VPN for off-site personnel, there are no risks on the security front and furthermore, to ensure even more robustness to the application, the source code implements the constructs to avoid SQL-Injection. All operations and user requests are traced on the database, the schema that is presented highlights the sequence of operations and the moment in which each event is stored in the table; user actions are made anonymous before logging.

Fig. 5: Page rendering steps

To maximize the effectiveness of the user experience, it will be necessary to simplify as much as possible the controls available to the user; for this reason, also referring to the habits of most Internet users, the basic search will be developed with a single textbox type control to be able to enter keywords and a button to start the search. Beside this it must be possible, through a further selector, to perform a 'simple' search (key search on the company name only) or on the entire subset of attributes defined as 'advancedSearch'. The page will therefore offer, in Google-like style, a text box for entering the search key, two selectors for customizing the behavior of the search engine (in particular for isolating the results from customer companies and for from the company name to all the fields indicated as searchable) and the button to submit the form.

Fig. 6: Search page mockup

The results of searches based on both simple and advanced searches, are presented according to a structure that returns a set of data that originates from companies. The attributes of the companies that meet the search criteria, their order and the way they is presented is dynamic, generated at runtime, and depends on the configuration table on the database. It is also provided the pagination of the results and a way that allows navigation between the different pages of the results quickly and easily.

Fig. 7: Results page mockup

The single result detail page offers all the attributes that are visible to the logged in user, organized in detail cards (tabs) as indicated in the configuration database, defined as active and viewable and organized in the page as the configuration defines to appear.

Fig. 8: Single result detail page mockup

More options available to users are self completion on the search textbox, the "I feel lucky" option before starting a search, the "Maybe you were looking for" functionality, the highlighting of the keyword searched over the details pages, a preview linked to the on-mouse-over event to see TuttoDB's or Google's result if the query is submitted, a MyTuttoDb area in which store favourites searches, companies, results, private or public comments to entities in the database. It has also been provided a simple ranking mechanism to promote results searched and viewed by people who used the same keyword during the search to push at higher position best results.

To clarify pages organization, I provide a general overview of pages and their dependence. The following diagram illustrates in detail the dependency between them and what are the events following which a redirection to other resources is expected.

Fig. 9: Application map

The integration with corporate server regards Microsoft Active directory user authentication and access to contact details, Microsoft Exchange to push email messages containing links and comments user wants to share and Microsoft Sharepoint to retrieve current user picture to enrich MyTuttoDB's profile.

III CONCLUSION

All tasks described above were successfully completed in less than 6 months and the application has been published and is currently adopted by the user. Here is its actual appearance.

Fig. 10: the actual Tuttodb starting page

Some numbers:

Database source:9
managed field: 180
Distinct company: 7400
Userse: 180
Code rows C#.NET: 1400
Time to market: < 5 months